

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

D2.1

Inventory of success cases and go-to-business scenario

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Executive Summary

Within the context of the INNO4CFIs project, a project that aims to support reforestation techniques that improve the absorption of CO₂ and simultaneously promote significant environmental advantages with the focus on Carbon Farming initiatives, Work Package 2 focuses on the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus and stakeholder analysis. The specific objectives of Work Package 2 are the following:

- mapping existing Nexus methodologies
- assessing the Carbon needs of the involved in the project regions
- assessing the application of the identified Nexus methodologies in the project's four living hubs and
- building a Nexus tool for SMEs

The objective of Task 2.1 is the identification and compilation in an inventory of best practices and state-of-the-art Nexus solutions, including Carbon Farming initiatives, from various sources (recent literature, databases, experience, and lessons learnt from past and current projects, partners' networks, EU funded projects, publications and initiatives in European regions with low innovation levels) and to develop a go-to business scenario to be adopted by small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Task 2.1 has started in month 1 and will be completed at the end of the project (month 36).

The INNO4CFIs deliverable 2.1 presents the methodology for the creation of the inventory and the development of the business scenario, as well as analysis on the best practices compiled within the first five months of the project. In this period, the criteria used to evaluate the Nexus and Carbon Farming best practices were determined. Furthermore, thorough research from multiple sources to identify those practices and to document and compile them was conducted. For the compilation of information, spreadsheet templates were also created. The required information was categorized into five distinct parts: 1) Case study information, 2) WEFE Nexus approach/Carbon Farming approach, 3) Impacts and Benefits, 4) Scaling and 5) Governance, Policy and regulation framework. The methodology for the development of the inventory can be found in detail in Chapter 2.

In Chapter 3 of this deliverable, the results from the analysis carried out in the case studies accumulated within the first 5 months of the project are presented. Analysis was conducted on several aspects of the provided cases, such as the location of the intervention, the intervention scale and degree, the funding resources, the particular function of the implemented practice and its environmental and socio-economic impacts, its scaling potential, as well as its governance scheme and risks from its adoption.

In Chapter 4, an outline of the INNO4CFIs go-to-business scenario for SMEs, based on literature sources and the analysis of the cases in the best practices inventory, is included. It is identified that by incorporating Nexus and carbon farming methods into their activities, SMEs can improve their resilience, support environmental sustainability, boost their reputation, and potentially generate extra income by selling carbon credits or marketing sustainable products. The complete version of the business scenario will be presented in month 36 and is expected to align with the latest advancements in Carbon Farming. It is also anticipated that the innovative solutions offered by the project will draw increased investment into carbon

farming initiatives, thus enhancing local innovation ecosystems and enriching the competitive edge of the project's designated areas.

Finally, Chapter 5 contains a detailed workplan for the implementation of Task 2.1. It is expected that the inventory will be enhanced with new cases until the end of the project, where the final version of this deliverable will be submitted.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
CF	Carbon Farming
EIS	European Innovation Scoreboard
EU	European Union
GHG	Green House Gases
Information and communication technologies	ICT
Interregional Innovation Investments	I3
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WEFE Nexus	Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem Nexus
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Climate change constitutes an extremely serious threat with consequences in the natural environment (biodiversity, soil, availability of fresh water, droughts, wildfires, floods, etc.), in public health, as well as the economic sector (e.g. infrastructure) [1]. Economic ramifications are expected to be more severe for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in terms of property damage, disruption of supply chains and business operations [2].

Reduction of greenhouse global emissions to zero by 2050 has been at the forefront of EU's policy and is one of the main targets of the European Green Deal, in order to mitigate climate change effects [3]. One of the proposed actions to capture CO₂ from the atmosphere is the adoption of Carbon Farming Initiatives. Carbon Farming (CF) refers to practices at the farm level including the management of land and livestock, pools of carbon in soils, materials, and vegetation and GHG fluxes [4]. At the same time, the climate change effects also ought to be addressed by adopting better practices of managing vital resources, such as water, energy, and food, as well as recognize their interconnections. Based on the latter, in the last years, scientists, researchers and policy makers have adopted the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem Nexus approach, a framework that emphasizes the interactions between those sectors and promotes integrated planning strategies [5].

Considering these factors, the INNO4CFIs project aims to advocate for reforestation methods that enhance CO₂ absorption while also fostering important environmental benefits. These benefits include sustainable freshwater generation, restoration of arid lands and soil health, and the promotion of biodiversity. The project will provide financial support to highly innovative technologies developed by SMEs located in eligible countries for Interregional Innovation Investments (I3) Instrument (EU27). Carbon Farming techniques will be the primary focus of the project.

Within the context of the project, WP2 aims to map existing Nexus methodologies and assess the CF needs of the involved in the project regions (Tuscany, Attica, Castile and León, Wallonia), with the goal to examine the application of the identified Nexus methodologies in the four living hubs and build a Nexus tool for SMEs. The objective of Task 2.1 is the identification of best practices and state-of-the-art Nexus solutions from recent literature, databases, experience, and lessons learnt from past and current projects, partners' networks, as well as EU funded projects, publications, and initiatives in European regions with low innovation levels. Within this task, a go-to business scenario will also be created to be adopted by SMEs, built on the results of the inventory's case studies analysis. A scheme of Task 2.1 is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Schematic presentation of Task 2.1.

The findings from Task 2.1 will serve as a foundation for Task 2.2 “Needs identification for low and moderate innovative regions” and Task 2.3 “Nexus assessment in the demo sites”.

2. Development of Nexus and Carbon Farming best practices inventory

The creation of the INNO4CFIs Nexus and Carbon Farming best practices inventory is part of Task 2.1, that has started in month 1 (September 2023) and will continue until the end of the project (M36). Building a best cases inventory involves several steps to identify, evaluate and categorize the various practices. The first step of our methodology included the determination of the criteria that will be used to evaluate the cases. The next step (ongoing) is to conduct thorough research from various sources to identify those practices and to document and compile them. For the compilation of information, spreadsheet templates were created. The inventory will be continuously updated until the end of the project and the information will be disseminated in two deliverables. In the next sections of this chapter, the process for the creation of the inventory is described in detail.

2.1 Purpose of inventory

The creation of a best practices Nexus and CF inventory will serve as a valuable resource primarily for the development of the go-to-business scenario, and secondarily for the rest of the tasks in WP2. By documenting and analysing best practices, the INNO4CFIs team will be able to learn from previous success stories and understand the contributing factors. Best cases can also serve as benchmarks where current performance can be measured.

2.2 Sources of case studies

The best practices inventory will be built with the use of various sources where case studies can be extracted, as a means to accumulate a diverse range of practices. The following sources will be used:

- **Online Platforms and Databases:** Potential databases that will be used for the identification of case studies include [Nexus Resource Platform](#), [Water-Energy-Food Nexus Knowledge Action Network \(WEF-KAN\)](#), [FAO's WEFE Nexus Platform](#), [Oppla](#), [Zenodo](#).
- **Scientific journals:** Platforms and repositories like Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Springer, Science Direct and MDPI will be utilized.
- **Consortium Partners:** The project involves 14 partners from eight countries (private companies, academic and research organizations, and regional authorities) with different expertise and networks. Their contribution to the inventory will be requested throughout the project, at specific time periods.

2.3 Development of the case studies templates

Two (2) templates were designed by NTUA to collect and categorize information on Nexus and CF best practices. The case study data collection templates were developed through analysis of case studies from a range of sources (literature, databases), including also experience from previous projects (Horizon2020 project [HYDROUSA](#), Prima project [SureNexus](#)), which informed the baseline of data availability and types of data. The focus for the development of the templates was to meet the data requirements of WP2 and at the same time, the resulting inventory to be used by as many partners as possible in other WPs (WP3, WP6 and WP7). To achieve that, an iterative process of collaboration, feedback, and consultations was followed internally within the INNO4CFIs consortium. The required information was categorized in five distinct parts:

1. Case study information
2. WEFE Nexus approach/CF approach
3. Impacts and Benefits
4. Scaling
5. Governance, Policy and regulation framework

Part 1 of the templates asks for general information of the case study, including a short description of the project and the implemented solution, location data, implementation date, the intervention scale and degree, the delivery stage and the funding and financing sources (Table 1). In some sub-sections, there was the option to choose from a list.

Table 1 Part 1 of the templates (Case study information).

Case Study information
➤ Project name and short description of the project
➤ Website

Case Study information	
➤	Location Data
➤	Implementation Date
➤	Lead organization/institution and Contact person
➤	Description of the implemented solution/s
➤	Intervention scale <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Micro • Meso • Macro
➤	Intervention Degree / Engineering level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better use of protected/natural ecosystems (no, or low human intervention) (1) • Sustainability and multifunctionality of managed ecosystems (medium human intervention) (2) • Design and management of new ecosystems and eco-technologies (strong human intervention) (3)
➤	Delivery stage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot • Under construction • Fully implemented • Scaling-up in progress • Other
➤	Funding and financing sources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market-based • Public sector/Research funding • Voluntary commitments • Other

In **part 2** of the templates the Nexus and Carbon Farming approach was addressed (Tables 2 and 3). The information requested include the components of the Nexus (Water, Energy, Food/By-products, and Ecosystems) addressed by the implemented solutions, the adopted carbon farming practices, the mitigation actions, if information and communication technologies (ICT) have been used and the key performance indicators (KPIs), that were monitored to evaluate the effectiveness of the solution. In the sub-sections “*Solution function/benefits*” and “*Mitigation Actions*” lists of different WEFE Nexus solutions and CF functions were included. Those lists were compiled by using scientific journals [6, 7, 8, 9, 10], reports [11, 12, 13, 14] and experience from previous projects [15].

Table 2 Part 2 of the templates (WEFE Nexus approach).

WEFE Nexus approach
<p>➤ Components of the WEFE Nexus that are addressed by the solution/s</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water • Energy • Food/By-products • Ecosystems
<p>➤ Solution function/benefits</p>
<p>➤ WEFE Nexus interconnections</p>
<p>➤ Use of information technologies (ICT)</p>
<p>➤ KPIs measured/monitored</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indicator • Method of verification/quantification • Additional information

Table 3 Part 2 of the templates (Carbon Farming approach).

Carbon Farming approach
<p>➤ Carbon Farming practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land Use • Cropland Management • Livestock and Manure Management • Nutrient & Soil Management • Other
<p>➤ Mitigation actions</p>
<p>➤ Use of information technologies (ICT)</p>
<p>➤ KPIs measured/monitored</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indicator • Method of quantification • Additional information

In **part 3** of the templates (Table 4), information is requested on the general impacts and benefits, as well as on specific impact categories. Four (4) impacts and benefits categories were identified as most relevant in the needs identification period for the creation of the templates, including: 1) Climate

change/Environmental, 2) Social, 3) Economic and 4) Institutional/Governance impacts. Specific lists were provided, but the option to complete a free answer was also available. The provided lists were adjusted accordingly based on the approach.

Table 4 Part 3 of the templates (Impacts and Benefits).

Impacts and Benefits
➤ General impacts and benefits
➤ Co-benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change/Environmental • Social • Economic • Institutional/Governance • Other

Part 4 of the templates (Table 5) refers to the scaling potential and the economic viability of the case studies. Scaling potential was included because it refers to the capability of a solution to expand its reach, impact, and effectiveness and will be useful in the development of the business scenario. Assessment of economic viability was included for the similar rationale.

Table 5 Part 4 of the templates (Scaling).

Scaling
➤ Horizontal scaling (Replication potential of the implemented solution/s)
➤ Vertical scaling (Scale-up potential of the implemented solution/s)
➤ Economic viability of the implemented solution/s

In the last part (**part 5**), information on the policy and regulation framework, the governance scheme, the involved actors (public institutions, private sector, etc.) and the risks and trade-offs associated with the implemented solutions is requested. More information about this part can be found in Table 6.

Table 6 Part 5 of the templates (Governance, Policy and regulation framework).

Governance, Policy and regulation framework	
➤ Policy and regulation framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current state • Expected contributions from the case study
➤ Governance scheme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bottom-up community initiative • Public/private cooperation • Private sector initiative • Public initiative • Multi-actor initiative
➤ Actors involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public institutions • Private sector • Research/Academia • Civil society • Other
➤ Risks and trade-offs	

3. Nexus and Carbon Farming case studies analysis

By the end of month 5 (January 2024), an initial number of 17 projects/case studies has been contributed to the inventory by the INNO4CFIs consortium members. In total, nine Nexus and eight CF projects were provided, with three belonging to both categories. It is important to note that certain projects included different solutions, that were applied across various countries and demonstration sites. In this section of the deliverable, the presentation of the results will be carried out, according to the categorization of the templates.

3.1 Case study information

3.1.1 Location of implemented solutions/interventions

Figure 1 presents a map of the countries where Nexus and CF solutions have been implemented from the accumulated cases. The results indicate that the provided solutions have been implemented in various countries in Europe, Asia, Africa, and South America. The countries that appear more times (more demo sites) are indicated with the darkest colour (i.e. Greece and Italy). It's important to highlight that while

interventions have been executed across multiple continents, the coordinating organization in all projects, but one, was located in a European country.

Figure 2 Locations (countries) where Nexus and Carbon Farming solutions have been implemented.

Additional analysis was performed and included in Table 7, to further characterize the identified European countries based on their level of innovation, as assessed by the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS). The EIS provides a comparative assessment of the research and innovation performance of EU Member States, other European countries, and regional neighbours, helping them assess the relative strengths and weaknesses of their national innovation systems and identify challenges that need to be addressed. The analysis on the provided case studies indicated that out of the 18 countries, eight were strong innovators, while the rest were evenly distributed between moderate and emerging innovators. As part of Task 2.2, further investigation will be conducted on the innovation level in the regions involved in INNO4CFIs.

Table 7 Innovation level of the European countries in the inventory according to the results of the EIS 2023.

Innovation Level/Performance Group	Countries
Strong innovator	Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, United Kingdom
Moderate innovator	Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Spain
Emerging innovator	North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia

3.1.2 Intervention scale, degree, and delivery stage

In the majority (57%) of the reported cases, the intervention scale was Meso, which indicates that the Nexus or carbon farming solution was implemented on a multi-farm or multi-facility scale. At a Macro scale (region scale), only a reported 36% of the solutions were implemented (Figure 3(a)).

In Figure 3 (b), the intervention degree is presented. In 62% of the reported cases, the intervention degree was at level 2, which indicates medium human intervention with the focus on the sustainability and multifunctionality of the managed ecosystems.

Regarding the delivery stage of the solutions (Figure 3 (c)), 29% of the solutions were reported as fully implemented, while 21% were at a pilot stage. A 21% of solutions was also reported as being scaled-up.

Figure 3 Schematic presentation of the Intervention Scale (a), Intervention degree (b) and delivery stage (c) of the reported case studies.

3.1.3 Funding and financing sources

Analysis on the answers in the sub-section regarding the funding and financing sources (Figure 4), indicated that in the majority (71%) of the provided projects, the project received funding from the public sector

and/or a research grant from an EU research and innovation funding programme or foundation, such as Horizon, PRIMA foundation, etc. Only 14% of the projects were reported as market based, while the rest received funding from several sectors.

Figure 4 Funding and financing information on the reported case studies.

3.2 Nexus and Carbon Farming approach

The provided case studies cover a wide range of Nexus and Carbon Farming solutions and practices, including circular economy solutions in food industries, regenerative and nature-based water solutions for nature-based water management, innovative approaches in the agroforestry and agriculture sector, solutions to produce healthy and sufficient food with less resources, market-based tree planting services, and more.

Regarding the projects targeting Nexus practices, nearly every solution addressed all facets of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems (WEFE) Nexus. Figure 5 illustrates the functions with the greatest proportions addressed by each solution in relation to every Nexus component. Within the water category, 30% of solutions focused on water reuse, whereas 27% contributed to water conservation. In the energy sector, 38% of solutions focused on energy savings, while 22% on energy production, mainly solar energy. In the food sector, 32% of solutions prioritized the reuse of organic waste, while in the ecosystems group, both reduction of water contamination and increase of biodiversity each accounted for 19% of the initiatives.

Figure 5 Functions with the highest percentages addressed by each solution in relation to every Nexus component.

Figure 6 demonstrates the carbon farming practices identified through the analysis as being most frequently implemented. Cropland management and land use were the most used practices with 28% equally, followed by nutrient and soil management with 24%.

Figure 6 Percentage of implementation for carbon farming practices.

Figure 7 illustrates the mitigation actions with the greatest proportions addressed by each solution in relation to every carbon farming practice. In the two mostly implemented categories, agroforestry solutions were preferred (36%), with management of existing woodland, hedgerows, etc. following closely (29%) (land use category). For cropland management, in 31% of the cases, several different strategies were applied, such as irrigation according to meteorological and soil moisture data.

Figure 7 Mitigation actions with the highest percentages addressed by each case study in relation to each Carbon Farming general category.

It's worth mentioning that nearly all case studies employed some form of information technology (ICT), such as sensors to monitor specific parameters, databases, models, and artificial intelligence, among others. The utilization of ICT suggests a shift towards data-driven decision-making processes and highlights the innovative approaches adopted in case studies. However, while case studies demonstrate the significant role of ICT in various domains and offer valuable insights into specific applications, they may not always be fully representative of the entire body of research in these areas, since the inventory will be enhanced with more cases.

3.2.1 Key Performance Indicators

During the analysis process of the provided case studies, several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were identified and categorized in eight groups, covering a wide range of the Nexus:

1. Water
2. Energy
3. Food/By-products
4. Ecosystem
5. Soil
6. Carbon sequestration
7. Economy
8. Social

Each group represents a strategic focus area within the Nexus, highlighting key dimensions that are critical for sustainable development. The identification of specific KPIs within each group facilitates the measurement and evaluation of outcomes related to water management, energy efficiency, agricultural productivity, environmental conservation, socio-economic development, and other relevant factors, while also reflecting an interdisciplinary perspective, recognizing the interconnectedness of different elements within the Nexus.

In Tables 8-15, all the identified KPIs can be found, with the inclusion of the method that was utilized to quantify each KPI and the number of KPIs identified in each category. In total, 64 KPIs were identified. The category with the most indicators was the Food/By-products (17), followed by the Water category, with 12 indicators. The remaining categories had 9 or less indicators, with the social group having the lowest, with three. The results of the KPIs will be further elaborated and used to build on Task 2.3.

Table 8 Identified Water KPIs with the corresponding method of verification/quantification.

Water KPIs	Method of Verification/Quantification
Conserved freshwater/water	Sensors
Quantity of water used in industrial processes/energy production	Sensors, Model
Quantity of wastewater produced from industrial processes	Sensors
Quantity of water used in agriculture/crop and food production	Sensors, Model

Water harvested and reclaimed (quantity and quality)	Sensors, Laboratory analyses
Collected rainwater and stormwater	Sensors
Water used for aquifer recharge	Sensors
Quantity of water reused in agriculture	Sensors, Laboratory analyses
Production of drinking water	Sensors, Laboratory analyses
Quantity of treated seawater	Sensors
Production of freshwater from saltwater/brine	Sensors
Water quality (physicochemical and microbial parameters)	Sensors, Laboratory analyses
Total Water KPIs: 12	

Table 9 Identified Energy KPIs with the corresponding method of verification/quantification.

Energy KPIs	Method of Verification/Quantification
Energy consumption	Sensors
Energy savings	Sensors
Reduction of the total energy intake	On-site data
Energy production (solar)	Sensors
Energy recovery (from industrial processes)	Data
Biogas production	Sensors
Fossil fuel consumption	Data
Total Energy KPIs: 7	

Table 10 Identified Food/By-products KPIs with the corresponding method of verification/quantification.

Food/By-products KPIs	Method of Verification/Quantification
Agriculture yields, crop production	Unspecified
Food production	Measurement
Vegetable production	Measurement
Aromatic plants production	Measurement
Essential oils production	Measurement
Fruit production	Measurement
Fruit export volume	Measurement
Fish production	Unspecified
Reduction of waste and by-products	Unspecified
Extraction yield of valuable compounds (nutrients recovery)	Unspecified
Reduction of organic waste	Calculations based on amount of compost produced
Growth of plants depending on the irrigation method	On-site measurements
Simultaneous production of salt (solar desalination)	On-site measurements
Fertilizer use saving	Calculations based on amount of food produced
Nutritional state of the plants	Laboratory analyses
Nutritional variety [food group count]	Score and weights survey
Area irrigated from collected rainwater	Sensors, On-site measurement
Total Food/By-products KPIs: 17	

Table 11 Identified Ecosystem KPIs with the corresponding method of verification/quantification.

Ecosystem KPIs	Method of Verification/Quantification
Invasive species composition	Unspecified
Physiological response of poplar MSA clones to drought conditions	Sensors
Biodiversity	Laboratory analyses
Agricultural biodiversity [Gini–Simpson index]	Score and weights survey
Non-CO ₂ GHG emissions - N ₂ O, CH ₄ -	Unspecified
CO ₂ reduction	Unspecified
Species planted	Geotag data and picture
Number of trees planted	Geotag data and picture
Water pollution/Sediment quality and quantity (in river basins)	Laboratory analyses
Total Ecosystem KPIs: 9	

Table 12 Identified Soil KPIs with the corresponding method of verification/quantification.

Soil KPIs	Method of Verification/Quantification
Soil fertility and biochar toxicity for plants	Laboratory analyses
Nutritional state of soil	Laboratory analyses
Soil moisture content	Sensors
Soil Organic Carbon	Laboratory analyses
Soil carbon	Satellite data, Laboratory analyses

Soil chemical properties	Laboratory analyses
Total Soil KPIs: 6	

Table 13 Identified Carbon Sequestration KPIs with the corresponding method of verification/quantification.

Carbon Sequestration KPIs	Method of Verification/Quantification
Plant carbon sequestration	Sensors
Soil carbon sequestration	Laboratory analyses
CO ₂ sequestered [metric ton CO ₂ eq]	Model, Satellite data
Tree carbon sequestration	Sensors
Total Carbon Sequestration KPIs: 4	

Table 14 Identified Economy KPIs with the corresponding method of verification/quantification.

Economy KPIs	Method of Verification/Quantification
Economic sustainability for farmers to realize poplar plantations	Economic data
Reduction of production cost	Calculation
Decrease import of tropical fruits	Calculation based on fruit production on -site
Farmer income [CRU revenues]	Score and weights survey
Number of beneficiaries	Data collection on the farmers participating in the plant distribution
Socio-economic indicators	Diagnostic tests
Total Economy KPIs: 6	

Table 15 Identified Social KPIs with the corresponding method of verification/quantification.

Social KPIs	Method of Verification/Quantification
Training on Agroforestry	Data collection on the hours of training
Social Impact	Data collection and Interview
Socio-economic indicators	Diagnostic tests
Total Social KPIs: 3	

3.3 Impacts and benefits

Within the framework of Task 2.1, analysis on the impacts and benefits of the reported implemented solutions was also conducted. Four impacts and benefits categories were included: 1) Climate change/Environmental, 2) Social, 3) Economic and 4) Institutional/Governance impacts.

Figure 8 (a) and (b) illustrates the climate change/environmental impacts and benefits for the Nexus and CF approaches. *“Availability of water during droughts”* and *“enhanced functioning of ecosystems”* were prioritised respectively, with a percentage of approximately 29%. The Social impacts are presented in Figure 9 (a) and (b). The most prominent benefit identified in both approaches were the opportunities for acquiring new skills, knowledge, and engaging in collective activities (~28%). The Economic impacts are depicted in Figure 10 (a) and (b). In the Nexus cases, the most important economic benefit was the reduction of loses (through circular economy approaches) (29%), while for CF, *“Increased farm income”* was prioritised (31%). Lastly, the Institutional/Governance impacts are presented in Figure 11 (a) and (b). In the Nexus cases, the most prominent benefit identified was opportunities for networking and collaboration of different sectors (33%). For CF, the most prominent impact was *“Highlighting the need for Carbon Farming inclusion in local plans, with evidence from applied examples”* at 37%.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8 Climate change/Environmental impacts and benefits from the implementation of Nexus (a) and Carbon Farming (b) solutions.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9 Social impacts and benefits from the implementation of Nexus (a) and Carbon Farming (b) solutions.

(a)

(b)

Figure 10 Economic impacts and benefits from the implementation of Nexus (a) and Carbon Farming (b) solutions.

(a)

(b)

Figure 11 Institutional/Governance impacts and benefits from the implementation of Nexus (a) and Carbon Farming (b) solutions.

3.4 Scaling

Analysis on the scale-up and replication potential of the Nexus and Carbon Farming solutions was also conducted. As presented in Figure 12, 80% of the solutions had been or had the potential to be scaled-up in other applications. For the horizontal scaling, the percentage was at only at 53%, since in a lot of cases, information was not available. The results were also similar for the economic viability of the solutions.

Figure 12 Percentage of case studies with scaling and economic viability potential and/or information on them.

3.5 Governance, policy, and regulation framework

The last part of the templates offered information on the policy and regulatory framework, governance structure, stakeholders (public institutions, private sector, etc.), and the associated risks and trade-offs of the implemented solutions. For the purpose of this analysis, one of the most important conclusions, pertained to the governance structure. The results indicated that the most predominant scheme was a multi-actor initiative, potentially due to its efficiency and adaptability (Figure 13). The involved actors varied and belonged to several types of organizations, including public institutions, private companies, universities, and NGOs.

Figure 13 Schematic presentation of the governance scheme of the reported case studies.

The case study analysis also identified several risks in the implementation of Nexus and CF practices, including:

- Stakeholders’ readiness to adopt Nexus and Carbon Farming solutions
- Limited education or inadequate understanding of agroforestry
- Marginal community support or low community involvement
- Inadequate operational capacity
- Lack of regulation in the European carbon credit market

4. INNO4CFIs go-to-business scenario

SMEs can be considered the backbone of global economy, representing approximately 90% of businesses worldwide [16]. In the EU, they represent 99% of all businesses and as already mentioned, they are the most affected by climate change [17]. By integrating Nexus and carbon farming practices into their operations, SMEs can gain resilience, contribute to environmental sustainability, enhance their reputation, and potentially create additional revenue streams through carbon credit sales or sustainable product marketing [18]. However, it is crucial for them to approach the adoption of carbon farming or other sustainable practices strategically, considering the unique aspects of their operations and industries, the

goals, risks, and potential threats. Therefore, the creation of a go-to-business scenario for SMEs is a necessity and will be developed within Task 2.1.

A business scenario provides a framework for exploring and evaluating different courses of action within a particular business context, helping to guide decision-making and shape strategic direction. It includes key elements such as the business problem or opportunity, relevant stakeholders, external factors, potential solutions or strategies, risks and uncertainties, and anticipated outcomes. In Figure 14 the basic steps for the development of a business scenario are illustrated.

Figure 14 Basic steps for the development of a business scenario.

4.1 Business case for Carbon Farming

Carbon farming presents a viable business opportunity for SMEs, offering both environmental benefits and potential financial gains. However, like any business venture, it requires careful consideration of the costs, benefits, and market conditions [19, 20].

Some key points are:

- 1. Increased Farm Profitability and Resilience:** Carbon farming projects can increase farm profitability and resilience by capitalizing on underutilized land, diversifying revenue streams, accessing carbon-neutral market opportunities, reducing input costs, enhancing soil health, and increasing water retention.
- 2. New Source of Revenue:** Carbon farming is like taking on a new crop or breeding a new line of sheep. It is a business decision with costs and benefits. It has the potential to add to a farm enterprise, provide a new source of revenue, and contribute to the sustainability and profitability of the farming operation.
- 3. Works with Traditional Farming Practices:** Several case studies demonstrate that carbon farming works successfully with traditional farming practices, increases productivity and drought tolerance while reducing farm input costs, and provides farmers with new income streams.

- 4. Growing Demand in the Carbon Market:** The growing demand of the carbon market has led to new agricultural programs and pledges by agribusiness and food retailers resulting in opportunities for farmers to participate. However, it is crucial for a program to price the carbon higher than implementation costs to ensure farmer interest.

Based on literature research [21, 22] and partner input, three categories of business models related to carbon farming were identified.

Agricultural value-chain business model

This category of business model is adopted by farmers, who implement sustainable practices to enhance their products. They often market these products by emphasizing the “story” behind them. This approach relies on consumers’ growing readiness to pay more for sustainable products. These products are often sold through short-chain marketing. A well-known example of this business model is the “organic” label. No additional stakeholders need to be involved in this category of business models.

Business models involving carbon farmers and industry

Increasingly, companies are incorporating climate and sustainability aspects into their activities. However, achieving climate neutrality can be challenging for industrial players, due to unavoidable emissions. To compensate, these companies are exploring creative solutions, such as planting trees or investing in sustainable energy production in developing countries.

In such cases “Carbon agreement” with carbon farmers comes into play. In these agreements, companies invest in farmers’ efforts to sequester carbon and in return, the company can claim sustainable practices. This approach provides an alternative way for companies to offset their emissions and contribute to sustainability.

Business models involving carbon farmers and governments and institutions

Climate mitigation and adaptation are priorities for many governments, regional or local authorities, leading to the development of climate action plans. Carbon farming is often promoted as part of these plans. Governments or authorities can directly pay farmers for the ecosystem services they provide through sustainable farming techniques.

Prevalent business case

As analyzed in chapter 3.1.3 Funding and Financial sources, the majority of the examples in our success cases inventory is funded from public sources. This indicates that the Business models involving carbon farmers and governments and institutions are currently the most recognized. This observation reflects the current status quo in funding patterns within the Carbon Farming domain without implying that these models are inherently superior or that other models are not viable or valuable. Instead, it indicates the

prevailing trend where public funding has been more readily available or accessible for initiatives involving carbon farming and collaborations with governments and institutions.

4.2 Carbon credits

A promising business scenario for carbon farming involves the use of carbon credits that can be traded between stakeholders. In this model, one stakeholder pays another to reduce CO₂ emissions or increase carbon sequestration, and in return, they can claim the reduced CO₂ emissions to offset their own.

Business models based on carbon credit trading are typically initiated by governments and large companies due to their complexity.

As a recent Carbon Market Report by the European Commission outlines [23], the carbon credit business model is not only viable, but is also driving the green transition. The [EU Emission Trading System](#) was introduced in 2005. Since then, it helped bring down emissions from power and industry plants by 37%. What is more, Member States used on average 76% of their ETS revenue in 2022 to support climate and energy action, including measures to address the effects of the energy crisis and help people and businesses.

It is encouraging that in addition to the regulated ETS, the number of voluntary local carbon projects is also increasing. This can be accredited to the development of carbon certification frameworks. These frameworks provide a credible system for measuring, reporting, and validating carbon sequestration, enabling local projects to contribute to domestic emissions reduction.

Interestingly, the trend of interest in locally produced carbon credits is on the rise. Initially, companies often fulfilled their carbon offset requirements by investing in tree planting projects in developing countries. These projects, while beneficial, were geographically distant and disconnected from the companies' local operations.

However, the landscape is changing. Companies are increasingly looking towards local initiatives for carbon offsetting. This shift is largely influenced by consumers growing support for local businesses and their willingness to buy locally produced goods. Consumers are more conscious of their environmental impact and are showing a preference for supporting local farmers who employ sustainable practices.

In response to this consumer trend, companies are exploring local carbon offset projects, often investing in sustainable farming practices that increase carbon sequestration.

4.3 INNO4CFIs go-to business scenario

The general objective of the project INNO4CFIS is creating a high replicable and scalable business model in the Green and Carbon Farming sector. More specifically, INNO4CFIs will provide an innovative Carbon Farming Platform to the European market, which will enable any Green Tech stakeholders to measure in real time several types of data (CO₂ emission and savings, soil conditions, water necessity, etc.) as well as optimizing their resources due to the A.I. component.

Taking into account evidence collected in chapter 4, it becomes clear, that the proposed INNO4CFIs business model is following the latest developments in the Carbon Farming arena. We expect that innovative added-value solutions of the project will attract more investments into carbon farming initiatives. This will consequently strengthen local innovation ecosystems, enriching the competitive advantage of the targeted territories.

5. Next steps

The data collection process for the enhancement of the inventory will continue under Task 2.1 until the end of month 32, to ensure that the analysis team (NTUA) will have as much information as can be sourced in preparation for the final version of the INNO4CFIs go-to-business scenario for SMEs. Within M15-M17, a review process is expected to be conducted in order to analyze the existing case studies in the inventory and determine if corrective actions are required, such as updating the templates. The developed database will also feed into Task 2.2. In M17-M32, the inventory is expected to be updated with new cases from databases, literature, and the project's partners. In the final months (M33-M36), the business scenario will be finalized and the final version of D2.1 will be submitted to the coordinator, after internal reviews within the consortium and the incorporation of requested changes and edits.

Table 16. Workplan for Task 2.1.

Activity	Months	Description
Identification of required information	M1-M3 September- November 2023	Analysis of case studies from various sources by NTUA team
Creation of Nexus and Carbon Farming templates	M1-M3 September- November 2023	Creation of templates by NTUA team and feedback from consortium partners
Distribution of templates within the consortium	M4-M5 December 2023- January 2024	The finalized templates were distributed within the consortium for the contribution of case studies
Submission of 1 st version of D2.1	M6 February 2026	Preliminary analysis of the case studies in the inventory and creation of a first version of the go-to-business scenario
Enhancement of inventory	M7-M14 March 2024- November 2024	Input from databases, literature and INNO4CFIs partners
Review process of inventory	M15-M16 December 2024- January 2025	Review process to analyze existing case studies and determine if corrective actions are required
Enhancement of inventory	M17-M32 February 2025-May 2026	Input from databases, literature and INNO4CFIs partners
Analysis of inventory cases	M33-M35 June 2026-August 2026	Processing and analyzing the case studies and finalization of the go-to-business scenario
Submission of final version of D2.1	M36 September 2026	Review of results report by INNO4CFIs partners and finalization of deliverable

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